

THE DOMB APÉRY-LIMIT AND A PROOF OF THE RAMANUJAN MACHINE CONJECTURE Z2

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ABSTRACT. We prove the Domb Apéry-limit

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{D_n} = \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3),$$

where D_n are the Domb numbers and B_n is the rational companion sequence satisfying the same three-term recurrence with initial data $B_0 = 0$, $B_1 = 1$. As corollaries we obtain the identity

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{64^n}{n^3 D_n D_{n-1}} = \frac{56}{3} \zeta(3)$$

and a proof of the Ramanujan Machine continued-fraction conjecture Z2:

$$\text{PCF}((2n+1)(5n^2+5n+2), -16n^6) = \frac{12}{7\zeta(3)}.$$

The argument combines the level-6 eta-product parametrization of the Domb generating function with an Atkin-Lehner transformation law for a weight -2 Eichler integral and a Mellin-transform computation of the associated period polynomial.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let

$$(1) \quad D_n := \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k}^2 \binom{2k}{k} \binom{2(n-k)}{n-k} \quad (n \geq 0)$$

be the Domb numbers (OEIS A002895). Their ordinary generating function

$$\mathcal{A}(z) := \sum_{n \geq 0} D_n z^n$$

is the unique holomorphic solution at $z = 0$ of the third-order differential equation

$$(2) \quad [\theta^3 - 2z(2\theta+1)(5\theta^2+5\theta+2) + 64z^2(\theta+1)^3]y = 0, \quad \theta = z \frac{d}{dz}.$$

This sequence lies at the center of several Apéry-like phenomena: it admits hypergeometric and modular parametrizations, appears in the theory of random walks and Bessel moments, and it is exactly the sequence used

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by Cohen in his normalization of the Ramanujan Machine conjecture Z2 for $\zeta(3)$ [2, 3, 7, 8, 9].

The Apéry-limit

$$(3) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{D_n} = \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3)$$

for the rational companion sequence B_n is listed in Almkvist–van Enckevort–van Straten–Zudilin [1] as a known value, but that paper gives neither a proof nor a bibliographic pointer for the Domb case. On the other hand, Cohen’s Domb sum

$$(4) \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{64^n}{n^3 D_n D_{n-1}} = \frac{56}{3} \zeta(3)$$

appears in [3] in experimental form. The purpose of the present note is to fill this gap and to deduce from it the Ramanujan Machine continued fraction Z2.

The main results are the following.

Theorem 1.1 (Domb Apéry-limit). *Let $\{D_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be given by (1). Let $\{B_n\}_{n \geq 0} \subset \mathbb{Q}$ be defined by*

$$(5) \quad (n+1)^3 u_{n+1} = 2(2n+1)(5n^2 + 5n + 2)u_n - 64n^3 u_{n-1} \quad (n \geq 1),$$

with $B_0 = 0$ and $B_1 = 1$. Then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{D_n} = \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3).$$

Theorem 1.2 (Domb sum). *One has*

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{64^n}{n^3 D_n D_{n-1}} = \frac{56}{3} \zeta(3).$$

Theorem 1.3 (Ramanujan Machine conjecture Z2). *The continued fraction*

$$2 + \frac{-16 \cdot 1^6}{36 + \frac{-16 \cdot 2^6}{160 + \frac{-16 \cdot 3^6}{434 + \ddots}}}$$

converges and its value is

$$\frac{12}{7\zeta(3)}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\text{PCF}((2n+1)(5n^2 + 5n + 2), -16n^6) = \frac{12}{7\zeta(3)}.$$

The proof of [theorem 1.1](#) occupies §§3–6. [Theorems 1.2](#) and [1.3](#) then follow by finite-difference and continuant algebra.

2. DOMB RECURRENCE, COMPANION SEQUENCE, AND CONTINUANTS

The Domb numbers satisfy the well-known three-term recurrence

$$(6) \quad (n+1)^3 D_{n+1} = 2(2n+1)(5n^2+5n+2)D_n - 64n^3 D_{n-1} \quad (n \geq 1),$$

with $D_0 = 1$ and $D_1 = 4$; equivalently,

$$(7) \quad (n+2)^3 D_{n+2} - (2n+3)(10n^2+30n+24)D_{n+1} + 64(n+1)^3 D_n = 0 \quad (n \geq 0).$$

See, for instance, [4, Table 2, case 6(B)].

Let $\{B_n\}_{n \geq 0} \subset \mathbb{Q}$ be the unique sequence satisfying the same recurrence (5) and the initial values $B_0 = 0$, $B_1 = 1$.

Lemma 2.1 (discrete Wronskian). *Define*

$$W_n := D_n B_{n-1} - D_{n-1} B_n \quad (n \geq 1).$$

Then

$$W_n = -\frac{64^{n-1}}{n^3} \quad (n \geq 1).$$

Consequently,

$$(8) \quad \frac{B_n}{D_n} - \frac{B_{n-1}}{D_{n-1}} = \frac{64^{n-1}}{n^3 D_n D_{n-1}} \quad (n \geq 1).$$

Proof. From (5) and (6) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} W_{n+1} &= D_{n+1} B_n - D_n B_{n+1} \\ &= \frac{1}{(n+1)^3} \left(2(2n+1)(5n^2+5n+2)D_n - 64n^3 D_{n-1} \right) B_n \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{(n+1)^3} D_n \left(2(2n+1)(5n^2+5n+2)B_n - 64n^3 B_{n-1} \right) \\ &= \frac{64n^3}{(n+1)^3} (D_n B_{n-1} - D_{n-1} B_n) = \frac{64n^3}{(n+1)^3} W_n. \end{aligned}$$

Since $W_1 = D_1 B_0 - D_0 B_1 = -1$, induction gives the stated formula. Dividing by $D_n D_{n-1}$ yields (8). \square

Corollary 2.2 (finite telescoping identity). *For every $N \geq 1$,*

$$(9) \quad \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{64^n}{n^3 D_n D_{n-1}} = 64 \frac{B_N}{D_N}.$$

Proof. Sum (8) from $n = 1$ to $n = N$ and use $B_0 = 0$. \square

Proof of theorem 1.2 assuming theorem 1.1. Let $N \rightarrow \infty$ in (9). By theorem 1.1 the right-hand side tends to

$$64 \cdot \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3) = \frac{56}{3} \zeta(3).$$

\square

We next connect the Domb recurrence to the Ramanujan Machine continued fraction Z2.

Proposition 2.3 (continuants and Domb normalization). *Let*

$$a_0 := 2, \quad a_n := (2n+1)(5n^2+5n+2) \quad (n \geq 1), \quad b_n := -16n^6.$$

Define continuants by

$$P_{-1} = 1, \quad P_0 = 2, \quad Q_{-1} = 0, \quad Q_0 = 1,$$

$$(10) \quad U_n = a_n U_{n-1} + b_n U_{n-2} \quad (n \geq 1),$$

where $U_n = P_n$ or $U_n = Q_n$. Then

$$(11) \quad P_n = \frac{(n+1)!^3}{2^{n+1}} D_{n+1}, \quad Q_n = \frac{(n+1)!^3}{2^n} B_{n+1} \quad (n \geq 0).$$

Hence

$$(12) \quad \frac{P_n}{Q_n} = \frac{D_{n+1}}{2B_{n+1}}.$$

Proof. Set

$$\tilde{P}_n := \frac{(n+1)!^3}{2^{n+1}} D_{n+1}.$$

Using (6) with index n we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P}_n &= \frac{(n+1)!^3}{2^{n+1}} D_{n+1} \\ &= \frac{(n+1)!^3}{2^{n+1}} \cdot \frac{2(2n+1)(5n^2+5n+2)D_n - 64n^3 D_{n-1}}{(n+1)^3} \\ &= (2n+1)(5n^2+5n+2) \frac{n!^3}{2^n} D_n - 16n^6 \frac{(n-1)!^3}{2^{n-1}} D_{n-1} \\ &= a_n \tilde{P}_{n-1} + b_n \tilde{P}_{n-2} \end{aligned}$$

for $n \geq 1$. Also $\tilde{P}_0 = 2$ and $\tilde{P}_1 = 56 = a_1 \tilde{P}_0 + b_1 \tilde{P}_{-1}$, so $\tilde{P}_n = P_n$ by uniqueness for (10).

The same calculation with B_n in place of D_n gives

$$\tilde{Q}_n := \frac{(n+1)!^3}{2^n} B_{n+1}$$

satisfying (10). Here $\tilde{Q}_0 = 1$ and $\tilde{Q}_1 = 36 = a_1$, hence $\tilde{Q}_n = Q_n$. Formula (12) follows immediately. \square

Proof of theorem 1.3 assuming theorem 1.1. By construction, P_n/Q_n is the n th convergent of the continued fraction in theorem 1.3. From (12) and theorem 1.1 we get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{P_n}{Q_n} = \frac{1}{2 \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} B_{n+1}/D_{n+1}} = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3)} = \frac{12}{7 \zeta(3)}. \quad \square$$

3. MODULAR PARAMETRIZATION AND THE EICHLER INTEGRAL

We write

$$\mathcal{A}(z) := \sum_{n \geq 0} D_n z^n, \quad \mathcal{B}(z) := \sum_{n \geq 0} B_n z^n.$$

By construction, \mathcal{A} satisfies (2), while \mathcal{B} satisfies the inhomogeneous equation

$$(13) \quad [\theta^3 - 2z(2\theta + 1)(5\theta^2 + 5\theta + 2) + 64z^2(\theta + 1)^3] \mathcal{B} = z.$$

In ordinary differential form these become

$$(14) \quad \begin{aligned} & z^2(4z - 1)(16z - 1)y''' + 3z(128z^2 - 30z + 1)y'' \\ & + (448z^2 - 68z + 1)y' + 4(16z - 1)y = 0, \end{aligned}$$

for $y = \mathcal{A}$, and the same equation with right-hand side z for $y = \mathcal{B}$.

The modular parametrization is the level-6 eta-product identity (Chan–Zudilin; Zhou)

$$(15) \quad \xi(\tau) := -\frac{\eta(2\tau)^6 \eta(6\tau)^6}{\eta(\tau)^6 \eta(3\tau)^6}, \quad A(\tau) := \frac{\eta(\tau)^4 \eta(3\tau)^4}{\eta(2\tau)^2 \eta(6\tau)^2},$$

with

$$(16) \quad A(\tau) = \mathcal{A}(\xi(\tau)) = \sum_{n \geq 0} D_n \xi(\tau)^n.$$

See [9, (3.2)–(3.7)]; compare also [2].

The Atkin–Lehner involution relevant here is

$$(17) \quad W(\tau) := \frac{3\tau - 2}{6\tau - 3}, \quad W = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & -2 \\ 6 & -3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \det W = 3, \quad W^2 = -3I.$$

We use the usual slash operator for matrices of positive determinant:

$$(f|_k M)(\tau) := (\det M)^{k/2} (c\tau + d)^{-k} f\left(\frac{a\tau + b}{c\tau + d}\right), \quad M = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}.$$

From [9, (3.4), (3.7)] we have

$$(18) \quad \xi(W\tau) = \xi(\tau), \quad A(W\tau) = -\frac{(6\tau - 3)^2}{3} A(\tau),$$

that is,

$$(19) \quad A|_2 W = -A.$$

Define

$$(20) \quad E(\tau) := \frac{\mathcal{B}(\xi(\tau))}{A(\tau)}.$$

The next proposition identifies E with a weight -2 Eichler integral.

Proposition 3.1. *Let*

$$(21) \quad g(\tau) := \frac{E_4(\tau) - E_4(2\tau) - 9E_4(3\tau) + 9E_4(6\tau)}{240} = \sum_{n \geq 1} a_n q^n, \quad q = e^{2\pi i \tau},$$

where

$$(22) \quad a_n = \sigma_3(n) - \sigma_3(n/2) - 9\sigma_3(n/3) + 9\sigma_3(n/6).$$

Then

$$(23) \quad E(\tau) = -\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{a_n}{n^3} q^n, \quad \text{equivalently} \quad D^3 E = -g,$$

where $D = q d/dq = (2\pi i)^{-1} d/d\tau$.

Proof. Apply the third-order variation-of-constants construction of Yang [8, Lemmas 1–2] to the ordinary inhomogeneous equation (14) for \mathcal{B} . Since the leading coefficient in (14) is $z^2(4z-1)(16z-1)$, this gives

$$(24) \quad D^3 E(\tau) = \Phi(\tau) := \left(\frac{D\xi(\tau)}{\xi(\tau)} \right)^3 \frac{\xi(\tau)}{A(\tau)(1-4\xi(\tau))(1-16\xi(\tau))}.$$

Because $(D\xi)/\xi$ has weight 2, A has weight 2, and ξ is modular of weight 0, the function Φ is a modular form of weight 4 on $\Gamma_0(6)$.

A direct q -expansion from (15) gives

$$\Phi(\tau) = -q - 8q^2 - 19q^3 - 64q^4 + O(q^5),$$

while from (21) one has

$$-g(\tau) = -q - 8q^2 - 19q^3 - 64q^4 + O(q^5).$$

Thus $\Phi + g \in M_4(\Gamma_0(6))$ has vanishing Fourier coefficients through q^4 . Since $[\mathrm{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z}) : \Gamma_0(6)] = 12$, the Sturm bound for weight 4 and level 6 is $\lfloor 4 \cdot 12/12 \rfloor = 4$; hence, by Sturm's theorem [5, Theorem 3.13], $\Phi = -g$. This proves (23). \square

We record the L -function of g and its alternating twist.

Proposition 3.2. *The Dirichlet series of g is*

$$(25) \quad L(g, s) := \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{a_n}{n^s} = \zeta(s)\zeta(s-3)(1-2^{-s})(1-3^{2-s}).$$

Hence

$$(26) \quad L(g, 3) = -\frac{7}{24}\zeta(3).$$

Define the alternating twist

$$(27) \quad L^*(s) := \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(-1)^n a_n}{n^s}.$$

Then

$$(28) \quad L^*(s) = -\zeta(s)\zeta(s-3)(1-2^{-s})(1-2^{4-s})(1-3^{2-s}).$$

In particular,

$$(29) \quad L^*(3) = -\frac{7}{24}\zeta(3), \quad L^*(2) = 0, \quad L^*(1) = \frac{7}{4\pi^2}\zeta(3).$$

Moreover, for every $s \in \mathbb{C}$,

$$(30) \quad \Gamma(s) \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^{-s} L^*(s+3) = \Gamma(-s-2) \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^{s+2} L^*(1-s).$$

Proof. Equation (25) follows immediately from (22) and the classical identity

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\sigma_3(n)}{n^s} = \zeta(s)\zeta(s-3).$$

Substituting $s = 3$ yields (26) because $\zeta(0) = -1/2$.

For the twist, write $n = 2^r m$ with m odd. Since (22) implies

$$a_{2^r m} = 8^r a_m \quad (m \text{ odd}, r \geq 0),$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned} L^*(s) &= \sum_{m \text{ odd}} \frac{a_m}{m^s} \left(-1 + \sum_{r \geq 1} \frac{8^r}{2^{rs}} \right) \\ &= \sum_{m \text{ odd}} \frac{a_m}{m^s} \left(-1 + \frac{2^{3-s}}{1-2^{3-s}} \right) = -\frac{1-2^{4-s}}{1-2^{3-s}} \sum_{m \text{ odd}} \frac{a_m}{m^s}. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, removing the 2-Euler factor from (25) gives

$$\sum_{m \text{ odd}} \frac{a_m}{m^s} = (1-2^{3-s})L(g, s).$$

Combining these formulas with (25) proves (28). The values in (29) follow immediately, using the standard identity

$$\zeta'(-2) = -\frac{\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2}.$$

Finally, (30) is a direct consequence of (28) and the functional equation of the Riemann zeta function. Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned} &\Gamma(s) \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^{-s} L^*(s+3) \\ &= -\Gamma(s) \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^{-s} \zeta(s+3)\zeta(s)(1-2^{-s-3})(1-2^{1-s})(1-3^{-s-1}) \end{aligned}$$

and the two zeta functional equations transform the right-hand side into

$$\Gamma(-s-2) \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^{s+2} L^*(1-s). \quad \square$$

4. LOCAL ANALYSIS AT THE DOMINANT SINGULARITY

Let

$$(31) \quad \tau_* := \frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2\sqrt{3}}.$$

Then τ_* is the unique point of the upper half-plane satisfying

$$(32) \quad 3\tau^2 - 3\tau + 1 = 0,$$

and $W(\tau_*) = \tau_*$. By [9, (3.11)],

$$(33) \quad \xi(\tau_*) = \frac{1}{16}.$$

Thus the dominant singularity of $\mathcal{A}(z)$ corresponds to the order-2 elliptic fixed point τ_* . Write

$$z_0 := \frac{1}{16}, \quad \varepsilon := 1 - 16z.$$

Proposition 4.1. *The point $z_0 = 1/16$ is a regular singular point of (14), and its local exponents are*

$$0, \quad \frac{1}{2}, \quad 1.$$

Consequently, near z_0 one has expansions

$$(34) \quad \mathcal{A}(z) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \varepsilon^{1/2} + O(\varepsilon), \quad \mathcal{B}(z) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \varepsilon^{1/2} + O(\varepsilon)$$

for suitable constants $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \beta_0, \beta_1 \in \mathbb{C}$.

Proof. In (14) the coefficient of y''' has a simple zero at z_0 , so z_0 is a regular singular point. Substitute $z = (1-\varepsilon)/16$ and $y = \varepsilon^r$. Since $d/dz = -16 d/d\varepsilon$, the coefficient of ε^{r-2} in (14) is

$$-6r(2r-1)(r-1).$$

Hence the indicial equation is $r(2r-1)(r-1) = 0$, and the exponents are exactly 0, 1/2, and 1.

Now $A(\tau) = \mathcal{A}(\xi(\tau))$ and $B(\xi(\tau))$ are holomorphic in τ near τ_* . Since τ_* is an elliptic point of order 2 for the genus-zero group generated by $\Gamma_0(6)$ and W , the Hauptmodul ξ has ramification index 2 at τ_* ; equivalently,

$$(35) \quad \xi(\tau) - \frac{1}{16} = c(\tau - \tau_*)^2 + O((\tau - \tau_*)^3) \quad (c \neq 0).$$

Therefore $\varepsilon^{1/2}$ is a holomorphic local parameter in τ , and the expansions (34) follow. \square

Lemma 4.2 (transfer to coefficients). *The coefficients of \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} satisfy*

$$D_n \sim -\frac{\alpha_1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} 16^n n^{-3/2}, \quad B_n \sim -\frac{\beta_1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} 16^n n^{-3/2},$$

and hence

$$(36) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{D_n} = \frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1}.$$

Proof. By [proposition 4.1](#), both functions admit local expansions of the form

$$F(z) = c_0 + c_1(1 - z/z_0)^{1/2} + O(1 - z/z_0) \quad (z_0 = 1/16).$$

Since there is no other singularity on $|z| = z_0$, the Flajolet–Odlyzko transfer theorem applies; see [[6](#), Theorem VI.1]. It gives

$$[z^n]F(z) \sim -\frac{c_1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} z_0^{-n} n^{-3/2}.$$

Applying this to \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} yields the stated asymptotics and [\(36\)](#). \square

Lemma 4.3. *One has*

$$(37) \quad \frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1} = \frac{\frac{d}{d\tau}\mathcal{B}(\xi(\tau))\big|_{\tau=\tau_*}}{\frac{d}{d\tau}\mathcal{A}(\tau)\big|_{\tau=\tau_*}}.$$

Proof. Let $u = \tau - \tau_*$. By [\(35\)](#) we have

$$\varepsilon^{1/2} = \lambda u + O(u^2) \quad (\lambda \neq 0).$$

Hence [\(34\)](#) becomes

$$A(\tau) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \lambda u + O(u^2), \quad \mathcal{B}(\xi(\tau)) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \lambda u + O(u^2).$$

Differentiating at $u = 0$ gives

$$A'(\tau_*) = \alpha_1 \lambda, \quad \frac{d}{d\tau}\mathcal{B}(\xi(\tau))\big|_{\tau=\tau_*} = \beta_1 \lambda,$$

which proves [\(37\)](#). \square

5. ATKIN–LEHNER TRANSFORMATION LAW

We first compute the action of W on the Eisenstein combination g .

Lemma 5.1. *With W as in [\(17\)](#), one has*

$$\begin{aligned} E_4(\tau)|_4 W &= 9E_4(3\tau), & E_4(2\tau)|_4 W &= 9E_4(6\tau), \\ E_4(3\tau)|_4 W &= \frac{1}{9}E_4(\tau), & E_4(6\tau)|_4 W &= \frac{1}{9}E_4(2\tau). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently,

$$(38) \quad g|_4 W = -g.$$

Proof. Factor

$$W = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & -2 \\ 6 & -3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -2 \\ 2 & -3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -2 \\ 2 & -3 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathrm{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$ and E_4 is modular on $\mathrm{SL}_2(\mathbb{Z})$,

$$E_4|_4 W = (E_4|_4 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -2 \\ 2 & -3 \end{pmatrix})\bigg|_4 \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = E_4\bigg|_4 \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = 9E_4(3\tau).$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} W = \begin{pmatrix} 6 & -4 \\ 6 & -3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -4 \\ 1 & -3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 6 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

so

$$E_4(2\tau)|_4 W = 2^{-2} E_4 \Big|_4 \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} W = 2^{-2} E_4 \Big|_4 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -4 \\ 1 & -3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 6 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = 9E_4(6\tau).$$

Now $W^2 = -3I$, and for even weights k one has $f|_k(-3I) = f$, so $|_k W$ is an involution. Applying $|_4 W$ to the first two formulas gives the other two. Substituting these identities into (21) yields (38). \square

The next lemma is the special case of Bol's identity that we need.

Lemma 5.2. *For every holomorphic function F on \mathfrak{H} ,*

$$(39) \quad \frac{d^3}{d\tau^3} \left(\frac{(6\tau - 3)^2}{3} F(W\tau) \right) = \frac{9}{(6\tau - 3)^4} F^{(3)}(W\tau).$$

Equivalently,

$$D^3(F|_{-2} W) = D^3 F|_4 W.$$

Proof. A direct differentiation suffices. Since

$$W'(\tau) = \frac{3}{(6\tau - 3)^2}, \quad W''(\tau) = -\frac{36}{(6\tau - 3)^3}, \quad W'''(\tau) = \frac{648}{(6\tau - 3)^4},$$

repeated application of the chain rule shows that all terms involving F, F', F'' cancel in the third derivative, leaving exactly (39). Dividing by $(2\pi i)^3$ gives the D -version. \square

We now determine the period polynomial of E .

Proposition 5.3 (Atkin–Lehner law for E). *One has*

$$(40) \quad (E|_{-2} W)(\tau) + E(\tau) = \frac{7}{6} \zeta(3) (3\tau^2 - 3\tau + 1) = -4L(g, 3) (3\tau^2 - 3\tau + 1).$$

Proof. Set

$$H(\tau) := (E|_{-2} W)(\tau) + E(\tau).$$

By lemmas 5.1 and 5.2 and proposition 3.1,

$$D^3 H = (D^3 E|_4 W) + D^3 E = -(g|_4 W) - g = 0.$$

Therefore H is a polynomial of degree at most 2.

To determine it, restrict to the W -invariant geodesic

$$(41) \quad \tau(y) := \frac{1}{2} + \frac{iy}{2\sqrt{3}} \quad (y > 0).$$

Then $W\tau(y) = \tau(1/y)$ and, by (23),

$$(42) \quad F(y) := E(\tau(y)) = - \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(-1)^n a_n}{n^3} \exp\left(-\frac{\pi n y}{\sqrt{3}}\right).$$

Mellin inversion gives, for $c > 1$,

$$(43) \quad F(y) = -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{(c)} \Gamma(s) \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^{-s} L^*(s+3) y^{-s} ds.$$

By (30), the integrand is invariant under $s \mapsto -s - 2$. Using this symmetry, shifting the contour, and collecting residues at $s = 0, -2$ (there is no residue at $s = -1$ because $L^*(2) = 0$) yields

$$(44) \quad F(y) - y^2 F(1/y) = \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3) (1 - y^2).$$

Indeed,

$$\text{Res}_{s=0} = L^*(3) = -\frac{7}{24} \zeta(3),$$

while

$$\text{Res}_{s=-2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^2 L^*(1) y^2 = \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3) y^2.$$

Now, on the geodesic (41),

$$(E|_{-2} W)(\tau(y)) = \frac{(6\tau(y) - 3)^2}{3} E(W\tau(y)) = -y^2 F(1/y),$$

so (44) is exactly

$$H(\tau(y)) = \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3) (1 - y^2).$$

Finally,

$$3\tau(y)^2 - 3\tau(y) + 1 = \frac{1 - y^2}{4},$$

whence

$$H(\tau(y)) = \frac{7}{6} \zeta(3) (3\tau(y)^2 - 3\tau(y) + 1).$$

Since both sides are polynomials of degree at most 2 in τ and they agree on the infinite set $\{\tau(y) : y > 0\}$, identity (40) follows. \square

6. PROOF OF THE DOMB APÉRY-LIMIT

We first differentiate the transformation law at the fixed point τ_* . Since

$$3\tau_*^2 - 3\tau_* + 1 = 0, \quad 6\tau_* - 3 = i\sqrt{3}, \quad W'(\tau_*) = -1,$$

differentiating (40) at $\tau = \tau_*$ gives

$$(45) \quad E(\tau_*) + \frac{E'(\tau_*)}{2i\sqrt{3}} = \frac{7}{24} \zeta(3).$$

Indeed, differentiating the left-hand side of (40) yields

$$\frac{d}{d\tau} (E|_{-2} W)(\tau_*) + E'(\tau_*) = 4i\sqrt{3} E(\tau_*) + E'(\tau_*) + E'(\tau_*),$$

which equals $4i\sqrt{3} E(\tau_*) + 2E'(\tau_*)$; differentiating the right-hand side gives

$$\frac{7}{6} \zeta(3) (6\tau_* - 3) = \frac{7}{6} \zeta(3) i\sqrt{3}.$$

After division by $4i\sqrt{3}$ we obtain (45).

The same differentiation applied to (19) yields the derivative of A .

Lemma 6.1. *At the fixed point τ_* one has*

$$(46) \quad A'(\tau_*) = 2i\sqrt{3}A(\tau_*).$$

Proof. Equation (19) is equivalent to

$$A(W\tau) = -\frac{(6\tau - 3)^2}{3}A(\tau).$$

Differentiate and evaluate at τ_* . Since $W(\tau_*) = \tau_*$ and $W'(\tau_*) = -1$, we obtain

$$-A'(\tau_*) = -4(6\tau_* - 3)A(\tau_*) - \frac{(6\tau_* - 3)^2}{3}A'(\tau_*).$$

Because $(6\tau_* - 3)^2 = -3$, the last term equals $+A'(\tau_*)$, and the identity simplifies to

$$2A'(\tau_*) = 4(6\tau_* - 3)A(\tau_*) = 4i\sqrt{3}A(\tau_*),$$

which is (46). □

We now complete the proof.

Proof of theorem 1.1. From (20) we have

$$\mathcal{B}(\xi(\tau)) = A(\tau)E(\tau).$$

Differentiating at τ_* and using lemma 6.1 gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\tau}\mathcal{B}(\xi(\tau))\Big|_{\tau=\tau_*} &= \frac{A'(\tau_*)E(\tau_*) + A(\tau_*)E'(\tau_*)}{A'(\tau_*)} \\ &= E(\tau_*) + \frac{E'(\tau_*)}{2i\sqrt{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

By (45) the right-hand side equals $\frac{7}{24}\zeta(3)$. Therefore, by lemma 4.3,

$$\frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1} = \frac{7}{24}\zeta(3).$$

Finally, lemma 4.2 gives

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B_n}{D_n} = \frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1} = \frac{7}{24}\zeta(3),$$

as claimed. □

Remark 6.2. The proof shows that the relevant constant is *not* the naive CM-value $E(\tau_*)$. Instead, it is the linear coefficient of the Eichler integral at the order-2 elliptic point, namely

$$E(\tau_*) + \frac{E'(\tau_*)}{2i\sqrt{3}} = \frac{7}{24}\zeta(3).$$

This is the correct replacement for the false identity $E(\tau_*) = -L(g, 3)$.

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